

Sami H Atassi:

**Social Media, Revolution, and
Postcolonialism: Visualizing the Syrian
Revolution via Social Media**

**Postcolonial Interventions: An Interdisciplinary
Journal in Postcolonial Studies**

ABSTRACT:

Despite the fact that social media has played such a momentous role in fueling the Arab Spring, no study has attempted to concentrate on social media within postcolonial discourse, which is likely due to the recency of these events and the lack of postcolonial scholarship on the cultural influence of social media. Reading primarily from Edward Said's *Covering Islam* (1981), Melanie McAlister's *Epic Encounters* (2001), and Slavoj Žižek's commentary on the Syrian Revolution, my goal in this paper is to start the process of analyzing and situating the mechanisms of social media within the discourse of postcolonial studies. Moreover, the first section of this paper functions as a theoretical basis of how social media can shape revolutionary subjects and subjectivities. Hence, the second section shows how these Syrian subjects utilized social media as the space for their revolution of images within the postcolonial context. As a result of historical circumstances, the final section will turn to the abrupt manifestation of ISIS and explore the implications of their presence in Syria and, more importantly for this analysis, their re-presentations in mainstream media that have increasingly overshadowed the revolutionary cause.

Keywords: *Social media, revolution, postcolonialism, Syria, ISIS*

On October 19, 2009, extraordinary news struck the globe, garnering more attention than the swine flue epidemic or the war in Afghanistan. Sent by an out-of-work dot-com executive named Robin Sloan, the “pentagigatweet” (the five billionth tweet on Twitter) made the headlines of mainstream news agencies around the world (Keats 92). Though this news may seem as useless as most of the twittering on Twitter, reports on the pentagigatweet tell volumes about the state of mass media. If we are to take Melanie McAlister’s suggestion and read “visual media [...] as history,” then these reports on the pentagigatweet mark a shift in the way mass media represents images and produces cultures across disparate borders (244). Moreover, the television—once the center of mass media—has been replaced by computers, laptops, tablets, smart phones, and the like. And if Edward Said was right in arguing that “it [media] is the culture,” then it would seem that these mainstream media outlets were nailing their own coffins with every print in the press (*Covering Islam* 52). In other words, news of Sloan’s pentagigatweet made the cultural transition clear: an actor as engaged as the television during the Vietnam War, the Iranian Hostage Crisis, and the Gulf War, social media has become the center of mass media, presenting and re-presenting ideas, images, and events transpiring on local and global scales. Today, citizens of the postindustrial world—“switching center[s] for all networks of influence”—scroll through social media and see the news, whether they had originally intended to or not (Baudrillard 133). It would not be much of a surprise if a large portion of the online community read the news about Sloan’s pentagigatweet via Twitter.

One year following news of the pentagigatweet, news on the Arab Spring swept the pages of mainstream and social media. From the Arab world to the Western world, revolutionaries and activists of the Arab Spring called for political change in the rule of local governments, which included those of Algeria, Egypt, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, and Syria to name a few.

While images of demonstrations, marches, rallies, and strikes played pivotal roles in spreading awareness of and gaining (or not gaining) support for each revolution, the effective use of social media made the Arab Spring unlike any other revolution in human history. In a sense, with the systematic use of social media to catalyze a revolutionary sentiment and to develop a nationalist consciousness in each country, the Arab Spring is the first *revolution of images*. Turning to social media as an outlet for revolutionary, anti-hegemonic discourse is not surprising, especially if we look at Twitter's mission statement: "To give everyone the power to create and share ideas and information instantly, without barriers" ("About Twitter" 2014). Certainly, this statement would just encourage most to continue their pointless babble, but for the Arab world, which has been "learning *about itself*" by means of images, histories, and information manufactured in the West," this spoke to those who knew and were reminded that their sociopolitical system was nowhere near democratic (*Covering Islam* 56). To show the world that they too believe in sharing ideas without barriers, that they are not what mainstream media made them out to be, local activists in the Arab Spring began writing stories on Facebook and uploading images on Twitter as their form of civil resistance against local oppressions and global re-presentations of Middle Eastern societies.

Despite the fact that social media has played such a momentous role in fueling the Arab Spring, no study has attempted to place social media within postcolonial discourses, which is likely due to the recency of these events and the lack of scholarship on the cultural influence of social media. Relying primarily on Edward Said's *Covering Islam: How the Media and the Experts Determine How We See the Rest of the World* (1981, 1997), Melanie McAlister's *Epic Encounters: Culture, Media, and the U.S. Interest in the Middle East, 1945-2000* (2001), Frantz Fanon's *Wretched of the Earth* (1961), and Slavoj Žižek's recent commentary on the Syrian

Revolution, my goal in this paper is to start the process of analyzing and situating the mechanisms of social media within the discourses of postcolonial studies. Furthermore, I have chosen the Syrian Revolution as my subject of analysis for a number of reasons: (1) from the beginning of the Syrian Revolution to today, social media has been utilized by activists inside and outside of Syria, (2) the Syrian Revolution has been made so noticeable as a result of the mass genocide and exodus caused by state-terrorism and civil war, (3) and the sudden presence of the terrorist organization the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS/ISIL/IS) has reinvigorated Manichean dialogues of “Islam versus non-Islam,” “East versus West,” “civilization versus barbarianism,” and so on. The first section of this paper functions as a theoretical basis of how social media has shaped revolutionary subjects and subjectivities. Hence, the second section shows how these Syrian subjects utilize social media as the space for their revolution of images within the postcolonial context. As a result of historical circumstances, the final section will turn to the abrupt manifestation of ISIS and their war of images and explore the implications of their presence in Syria and, more importantly for this analysis, their re-presentations in mainstream media that have increasingly overshadowed the revolutionary cause. To quickly note, my use of labels throughout this paper is in no way an attempt to reduce the variety and complexity of human interests and experiences in times of revolution. As Said suggests, we must look at labels as having an identifying function and a function that produces much more complex meanings (*Covering Islam* 10). The different coalitions of revolutionary fighters in Syria (labeled by Western media as either “moderate” or “al-Qaida-linked”) and the doublespeak acronyms for the Islamic State (ISIS, ISIL, and IS) attest to this.

Revolutionary Subjects and Subjectivities Online

Social media is one of the resources I depend on daily. How and why I use different social media for respective purposes not only reflects my interests and who I am to friends and strangers, but also shapes and reshapes my subjectivity through practice, re-presentation, posts, and reposts—in short, (com)posts. My use of the term (com)post is intended to reflect the nature of post-criticism as Gregory Ulmer defines it: “the saprophyte, [...] feeding off the decay of tradition” (106). In the context of social media, new posts on my page live off of old posts, etc. Moreover, through social media, the meaning of my identity has become “a message to be encoded and decoded,” but what I encode as my self is never exactly decoded as the same self I had previously encoded—so I encode more (Hayles 79). On the other side of the transference, the way the receiver decodes my self seems nothing beyond a reflection of the viewer’s self in terms of what I originally encoded. To use Said’s phrase, social media are online “communities of interpretation” where people are “creating and revealing themselves and their interpretations as a very central feature of their existence” (Said 45). Although Said coined this expression to show how identity formation and knowledge production have been constructed through information provided by the media, the application of the term today can be quite useful. (Com)posts on social media are nothing more than diverse forms of “received interpretations” that provide the subjects with the terms of making meaning for themselves and their online communities (Said 46). Therefore, if social media is constituted by the technologies of television, radio, newspaper, film, mass communication, and more, then it would seem social media is the “cultural apparatus” *par excellence*, providing the subjects of communication with the “communal core of interpretation” (Said 47). Undoubtedly, there are varieties and differences in what is (com)posted, as there are varieties and differences within mainstream media, but there

remains certain rules, conventions, and images that shape the (com)posted material. Controlled by capitalist dynamics on every level, social media allows subjects, like myself, to construct and (com)post their selves and their interests through these very dynamics.

One of the major paradoxes regarding social media is the perception that one is free to share information to the world without any restrictions. If this were true, Twitter would not have a limit of 140 characters for each (com)post. Like culture, language, and nature, different types of social media are dictated by rules and understood through conventions that have been fashioned and passed down by other people. As Jean-François Lyotard predicted, electronic databanks and communication technologies will be “‘nature’ for postmodern man” (51). Nevertheless, as nature has shown us (rather, as we have shown nature), rules and conventions can be followed and challenged in the process of liberating the potentiality to create ostensibly new ideas and materials that may affect the surrounding environment for better or worse. In the time that McAlister wrote *Epic Encounters*, it was clear to Americans and much of the Western world that “[p]articipation in watching and shopping did not *reflect* experience, it *was* the experience” (241). Prior to social media, news on television reported the facts of the world as they were happening, while individual experiences were shared from person to person on a local scale. Social media has begun liberating the popular narrative from the re-presentation of images and stories that have become fixed, canonical, and binding. Watching television involves nothing beyond watching what everyone else is given to see; (com)posting on social media has involved the exhibition of local experiences, as well as the re-presentation of mainstream narratives. The liberating potential comes from this divide. While there exists respective rules for each site of social media, (com)posting stories and images that question and challenge the mainstream narratives is the first step to liberating the social consciousness and modifying the “communal

core of interpretations” (*Covering Islam* 47). In his essay “Opponents, Audiences, Constituencies” (1982), Said listed two tasks that must be undertaken in order to challenge and claim the discourse and vision fabricated by “a tiny handful of large and powerful oligarchies:” (1) “use the visual faculty [...] to restore the nonsequential energy of lived historical memory and subjectivity as fundamental components of meaning in representation” and (2) open “the culture to experiences of the Other which have remained ‘outside’” (157, 158). For once, the subaltern can speak (or tweet) to outside communities through the digital face of the world.

Initiating positive social and political progress involves a number of complex factors under unexpected historical conditions. Social media has become one of these factors in time. Increasingly, the words “politics” and “social media” are being uttered within different types of discussions. As Gary Chapman notes, technologies like social media are not neutral, but possess “political characters” that are shaped by its users (318). By demystifying the neutrality of social media, Chapman believes this is the first step to “reasserting our aspirations for a better future, organizing the political power necessary for implementation of those values, and then reconfiguring technology to reflect our aspirations” (318). Today, we see these processes taking place in various forms in both the East and the West. In the Arab Spring, activists planned and organized rallies and marches that were sporadically printed on headlines and incessantly uploaded on social media. In America, since the end of 2014, there has been a similar process, as Black Lives Matter activists fighting racial and social injustice have marched the streets in protest against the number of police officers who have killed African-Americans with impunity. What follows on social media is the development of the social consciousness regarding the particular sociopolitical revolt. No longer the television retelling the same story with different characters, users of social media are (com)posting their own images, ideas, experiences, and

responses that support, challenge, shape, and reshape the canonical illustrations of mass media superimposed on current events. As a result of this instantaneous flow of communication, the world's information is no longer controlled by the handful of oligarchs; instead, individual subjects online are shaping and providing the knowledge that will circulate through the networks of interpretation. The same technologies that have had such an impact on the sciences are now in the hands of the public who continue to revolutionize the way events, images, and individuals are projected to others. With social media replacing the supremacy of mass media, the masses now have an explicit role in developing the cultural apparatus. No longer shall mainstream media position itself "as the voice or [...] conscience of the People" (Hardt, Negri 311). For now, social media is the means by which the people can speak for themselves.

Because social media—like any other medium of discourse—has the ability to (re)produce knowledge and manipulate desire, there is reason to be concerned with its future form of disciplinization. In Foucauldian terms, the (com)posts on social media can be viewed as "a new regime of discourses," where different types of individuals speak on different matters from different points of view in order to obtain different results (*History of Sexuality* 27). In other words, sites of social media radiate discourses so that people become more aware of certain topics over others. Along with the body and word of the individual, accounts on social media have become objects of knowledge. Soon enough, the administrators, funders, programmers, and other professionals of social media websites will more heavily depend on the way people use social media in the process of shaping systems of social, political, and economic control. Like the body itself, the body of social media will fall in "the grip of very strict powers" imposing constraints, prohibitions, and obligations on its users (*Discipline and Punish* 136). Social media has been transforming into a mechanism for training citizens on what they should and should not

publically say, do, see, or know online. This machinery of control thus functions as a database of digital conduct where the website is the examination, the users provide the data for analysis, and the professionals police the content through algorithms and individual reports. For example, the Egyptian government has been known for monitoring the Internet activity on websites like gayegypt.com in order to impede gay Egyptian men from identifying their same-sex sexual practices with “the Western identity of gayness and the publicness that these gay-identified men seek” (Massad 382). In blaming this “deviance” on the new Western imposition, the Egyptian government is condemning and pursuing those who openly identify as “gay” through social and public activities that have become accepted in Western societies and online communities. Ironically, it seems the United States Department of Defense (DoD) has learned from the revolutions and the totalitarian surveillance societies in the Middle East. The DoD’s multi-million dollar “Minerva Research Initiative” examines the (com)posts on social media networks in order “to identify individuals mobilized in a social contagion and when they become mobilized” (Ahmed 2014). Increasingly, the sense of negative liberty will fade in relation to the practice of (com)posting on social media; over time, the utilization of social media ought to be mutually perceived as a positive liberty that has the potential to challenge the rules and conventions of the systems of social control.

(Com)posting and Visualizing the Syrian Revolution on Social Media

If it were not for social media, the Syrian Revolution would have had the same fate, for better or worse, as what is now known as the 1982 Hama Massacre. Because the media in Syria at that time was strictly controlled by the Baath party regime, information about the events—besides the details shared in private circles—naturally followed the mainstream narrative: the authoritarian president of Syria, Hafez al-Assad, was saving the fate of Syria by exterminating

the plague of the Islamic Brotherhood. It is not surprising that media outlets around the world readily accepted this story, since Islamic terrorism was on the verge of replacing Communism as *the* international threat. As President Reagan declared in his inaugural address in January 1981, “‘terrorism’ would replace ‘human rights’ as [America’s] primary foreign policy concern” (McAlister 199). Hafez al-Assad used the televised narrative to authorize the violent suppression of what Syrians today would refer to as a social rebellion that was utterly stamped and silenced from history. We know very little about this episode beyond speculation and myth, and Said admits to this in his critique of the fear mongering narrative of “‘the return to Islam’” (*Covering Islam* 65). The Muslim Brotherhood, according to Said, is one of the many “political actualities” that informed and corresponded with Western media’s reports on the threat of Islam; in turn, the truth of the matter has been buried under two layers of revolutionary rubble (65). Because international information about the outside world was configured and produced by mainstream media, the only narrative of the Hama Massacre that resonates with today’s viewers is that tens of thousands of Syrians died as a result of the Muslim Brotherhood. Unfortunately, as Ngũgĩ wa Thiong’o lamented the neglected incidents of the tortures at Hola, “[t]here were many horrors whose knowledge never went beyond the location of their commission” (17). However, a careful juxtaposition of those circumstances with today’s social activity could uncover a lost history of sociopolitical revolution.

Today, the Syrian government, ruled by Hafez al-Assad’s son, Bashar al-Assad, continues the tradition of labeling dissidents as Islamic fundamentalists or terrorists (Erllich 72). In short, the Syrian Revolution sparked as a result of the arresting and torturing of 15 Syrian boys between the ages of 10 and 15 who, on March 6, 2011, spray-painted messages calling for the fall of Bashar al-Assad’s regime: “‘As-Shaab / Yoreed / Eskaat el nizam!’: ‘The people /

want / to topple the regime!” (“How Schoolboys Began the Syrian Revolution” 2011). While older generations of Syrians had grown accustomed to the totalitarian state, the new generation saw the stories of their relatives manifesting before their eyes. With the flames of the Arab Spring already spread into Syria, the “spectacular measures” taken by the authorities, as Fanon wrote on the Algerian Revolution, did “not make the people draw back” (71). Aware of the representations of the Western press in the twenty-first century, thousands of Syrians took to the streets with banners and smart phones to call for the release of the boys, to engage in non-violent protests, and to show the world what they felt had to be seen. On that Friday, regime forces killed nearly 100 protestors across the country. The next day, at least nine were killed at the funerals for those who were gunned down on Friday. With the Daraa Massacre the following Monday, it seemed Bashar al-Assad wanted the Syrians to take up arms—and that is exactly what he intended. Assad learned from his father and the Western press that he could justify his actions if the propagandistic image of gun-wielding Arabs were to characterize the protesters (predominately Sunni Muslims), which would contaminate the revolution with the re-presented image of the media’s trope of militarized Sunni Muslims. As the brutality of the regime forces persisted, the protesters eventually took up arms, calling for national freedom.

A comparison between the Syrian Revolution and Fanon’s statement on the role of Western imperialism during the process of decolonization may shed light on the complexity of the West’s role in the Syrian Revolution. According to Fanon, “[b]oth capitalism and imperialism are convinced that the struggle against racialism and the movements toward national freedom are purely and simply directed by remote control, fomented from the outside” (80). In the case of the nascent stages of the Syrian Revolution, primarily Turkey and Saudi Arabia supported the struggle toward national freedom, but the resources they provided the Syrians were

not enough to turn the tables, since Bashar al-Assad's regime was backed by Russia, Iran, and China. The fomenting of mass media attempted to eclipse the images surfacing on social media, with intellectual commentators, like Slavoj Žižek, reductively stating—before ISIS ever manifested—that the Syrian Revolution was “drowned in the mess of fundamentalist groups” (“Syria Is a Pseudo-struggle” 2013). It is no wonder that Western heads of imperialism have been convinced that revolutionary struggles are controlled from the outside, since that is precisely what they have been attempting to do by re-presenting the Arab world in their own interests. Because the rebellious Syrians have been well aware of this, they have turned to the West, (com)posting images and videos on various social media platforms to spread global awareness and request for international support. For Žižek to reduce the Syrian Revolution to the idea of “a pseudo-struggle” is to ignore and silence the Syrians' call for Western aid. However, if Western powers did oblige by providing Syrians with adequate support to liberate Syria from the Baath party regime, then the imperial narrative would be contested: this movement toward national freedom *would not* be “purely and simply directed by remote control” (80). For this reason, among many others, the local images, videos, and stories shared on social media were repetitively questioned by mainstream media for their validity and were replaced by the counter-narrative, or mainstream narrative, that the aid to Syrian revolutionaries would end up in the hands of the enemy of the globe: the violent Islamic fundamentalists who seek to destroy the West.

If “representation of the event *was* the event,” then foreign audiences watching the Syrian Revolution unfold have been faced with deciding which representation they should believe to be the true event (McAlister 241). On the one hand, social media have been the spaces for (com)posting unverifiable images taken by individual Syrians within Syria; mainstream media,

on the other hand, has been taking events and (com)posts from Syria, questioning them, and then reformulating them into the familiar narrative that best fits the publishers' interests. Though the (com)posts on social media rarely parallel with the narratives told by mainstream media, we should read both narratives for what they are and where they come from. For instance, images of the revolutionary banners produced in the Idleb countryside, which have infiltrated the pages of mainstream media, are written in Arabic and English in order to reach local and Western audiences in the aim to skewer Bashar al-Assad and, now, ISIS (see Figure 1). Raed Fares and Ahmad Jalal are the local Syrians behind these productions, creating banners, images, and videos that are soon (com)posted on Facebook, Twitter, and Tumblr to name a few (Karam 2014). What Said referred to as the "rhetoric of power" is now being utilized in Idleb and across Syria to produce, not "an illusion of benevolence," but an image of anti-despotism and anti-imperialism within the grassroots of the revolutionary setting (*Culture and Imperialism* xvii). By utilizing the power of representation through social media, the online Syrian activist has "discover[ed] reality and transform[ed] it into the pattern of his customs, [...] and into his plan for freedom" (Fanon 58). Furthermore, he has encouraged and allowed the global audience to go "beyond what is commonly available to newsmen and newswomen" working outside of the society they are covering (*Covering Islam* 107).

However, to reestablish political interests within the region, mainstream media has worked to negate the revolution in the same way that the Iranian Revolution (or Islamic Revolution) had been dismissed by America in 1979 (*Covering Islam* 101).

Figure 1. Following the news of actor Robin William’s death, the artists and activists from Idlib, Syria created and (com)posted a banner displaying one of William’s lines during his role as the Genie in Disney’s *Aladdin* (1992). Banner and photo by the activists of *Occupied Liberated Kafranbel*.

The severe ambiguity in most reports from mainstream media outlets is a reflection of how the “oligarchs” want mass audiences to visualize the Syrian Revolution: it is a terribly ambiguous international crisis. While this is true, the reports do not address the social, political, or economic realities inside and outside of the borders of Syria. After drowning the audience in the redundant catalogue of information, the journalist’s report quickly turns to the anxiety that if the West were

to supply the Syrian revolutionaries with weapons, then they would inevitably fall in the hands of radical Muslims. Rather than analyze or report the sociopolitical circumstances being played out in the region, these articles rehash the same argument for why the West should not support the revolution: as Žižek put it, there is no “strong radical-emancipatory opposition” that the West can trust (“Syria” 2013). So the question arises, why does the West not help this opposition become strong enough to win the revolution? Coming full circle, it is because of radical Islam, which has become the canonized symbol of the Middle East for Western audiences in the past decades. Because of the threat of Islam, we can assume mainstream media cannot afford to spend time on understanding what the term “moderate rebels” entails and must focus that attention on the principal threats and foreign interests of the West. It is up to the viewer to differentiate between the imperialistic narrative and the truth of the matter. An online search followed by swift scrolls through different pages of social media will show who these “moderates” are: the Idleb community speaking to the world, the White Helmets digging through blocks of concrete, musicians like LaTlatch recording and producing politically-charged lyrics, reporters like James Foley sacrificing their lives, the Syrians recording barrel bombs falling from the sky. . .

The Virtual Reality of ISIS/ISIL/IS

In a response to the 9/11 attacks, Žižek reflected on the cognitive effect of viewing the catastrophic images on television, re-presenting the “ruin of all space, shattered glass and toppling masonry,” as James Joyce illustrated nearly a century before in *Ulysses* (1922) (22). In the same way that Stephen Dedalus and Leopold Bloom are psychosomatically disrupted by this fantastic image of destruction, viewers re-viewing the collapse of the Twin Towers were experiencing what Žižek had expressed: “It is not that reality entered our image; the image entered and shattered our reality” (“Welcome to the Desert of the Real” 386). Not referring to

Joyce, Žižek asked, where did we already see the same thing over and over again? In short, the amalgamation of re-presentations shaped and projected by the cultural apparatus. While most Americans, hopefully, learned that such events should happen in neither America nor anywhere else in the world, the propaganda of mainstream media echoed the Bush administration's declaration of the Global War on Terrorism. As a result, even the traditional Left in America and Europe has come to understand 9/11 (and its consequences) "as a battle between fundamentalism and democracy," or as Žižek defined it as active nihilists (Islamic radicals) versus passive nihilists (Western consumerists) ("Welcome" 387). While Žižek's interpretation is quite provocative, Spivak's commentary on the consequences of 9/11 center on its postcolonial effects. She has claimed that cities and countries, following the historical moment of 9/11, are being "transformed from space to data" (74). As social media has shown us, there is no denying this fact. Moreover, it is the "multitude" in social media who possess the potential in "confronting Empire head-on like the net(work) that brought down Agamemnon" (Spivak 75). Even Žižek admitted that this "vast network of social units [...] is the principal gain of the Arab Spring" ("Syria is a Pseudo-struggle" 2013). Unfortunately, Žižek went nowhere beyond analyzing this achievement so that he could return to the mainstream narrative and conclude that the Syrian Revolution is bound to fail because of the "strong presence of al-Qaida in the shadows" ("Syria" 2013).

Fostered in the prisons of Syria and Iraq, ISIS surfaced on the pages of mainstream media at the close of 2013. No longer the story of the fight to liberate Syria, the Syrian Revolution was further obscured by the re-presentation of ISIS on mainstream media. The very acronym "ISIL" ("Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant," which Obama has been using to denominate the group) is an attempt to remove Syria from the picture. As we have seen through 9/11, the Iranian

Hostage Crisis, and the Munich massacre during the 1972 Olympics, reports on terrorist activities have given those activities their desired legitimacy (McAlister 221). Richard Jackson's definition of the term "terrorism" is instrumental in analyzing the causes of terrorism beyond the narrative of radical Islamic fundamentalism: "Terrorism is violence or its threat intended as a symbolically communicative act in which direct victims of the action are instrumentalized as a means of creating a psychological effect of intimidation and fear in a target audience for a political objective" (Sinclair, Antonius 15). Hence, the purposes of terrorist acts are not the acts themselves, but are a means of achieving some other end, which is to manipulate the behavior of their target audience. By broadcasting and re-presenting the images of ISIS, mainstream media is fulfilling the aims of ISIS: to anger, disgust, scare, and confuse Western audiences, which in turn legitimizes terrorist activities through their very re-presentation in mainstream media. Audiences know to worry about ISIS because they have been told to do so by the "experts." However, instead of believing in the next war on the basis of "*essential values of justice*" (the antithesis of Islamic fundamentalism), viewers must interpret these reports in the frame of Jackson's definition of terrorism (Hardt, Negri 18). By allowing the re-presentations of ISIS to overshadow the lived experience of individuals suffering in the region, there can be no progress towards understanding the causes of ISIS's manifestation: the destabilization of the region due to the lack of international support for the Syrian Revolution, not to mention the aftermath of imperialist intervention in Iraq.

Figure 2. Moments before he beheads U.S. journalist James Foley, “Jihadi John” warns Obama against plotting against ISIS, or else he will take the lives of more Americans. Still image from video uploaded on YouTube. Courtesy of *New York Daily News*.

To come closer to an understanding of the crisis in Syria and Iraq, images like that of “Jihadi John” (see Figure 2) must be read through the history of Western interests and military interventions in the Middle East and in conjunction with the images and videos uploaded online by locals experiencing the event being visualized. It is not surprising that Western newspapers eagerly report beheadings in the Middle East, but we cannot allow the trope of decollation and radicalized Islam to evacuate history from lived experiences and geopolitical networks by reducing historical events to a narrative that separates Islam from the West, the civilized from the barbarians (Janes 10).

While the American imperium has occupied the center stage in world politics, the Arab Muslim and his/her world have been viewed as the major concern of the international community. With American media outlets using the re-presentations of ISIS to overshadow the images and stories shared by locals in Syria, the sociopolitical milieu of Syria is being reduced to the problem of radicalized Islam. As the Syrian revolutionaries continue to contend, ISIS did not materialize from ideologies of Islam, but was the result of regional conflict and geopolitical economies. In addition, rather than the ideologies of Islam, it was individual terrorists who disregarded international law by claiming control of lands with borders nearly as volatile as they had been after the fall of the Ottoman Empire. If we follow Néstor García Conclini's assertion and view borders "as 'laboratories of the global,'" we can see how the formation of ISIS across the borders of Syria and Iraq is a challenge against the capitalist way of being "by contesting the 'pattern of the world' that establishes the conditions for capital's flourish and regular crises" (Mezzadra, Neilson 62, 59). On one hand, the international community continues to recognize the border between the modern states of Iraq and Syria; on the other hand, members of ISIS are the only individuals who have vocalized their disregard for the Iraq-Syria border. Collaborative research on this contested borderland region will show how processes of capitalist creation and destruction heavily depend on the features of the processes of remaking and re-marking nation-state borders. Knowledge of who and what is percolating through these porous borders is necessary for visualizing the sociopolitical reality of the region, as well as for providing insight into how the current geographic destruction and reformulation of Iraq and Syria will shape the way these borders are (re)drawn in the years to come. The same can be said regarding the information that penetrates borders through online activity on social media. (Com)posts on social media express the variegated knowledges that bear on particular borders being negotiated. By

tracing the way re-presentations from social and mainstream media have crossed these borders, light can be shed on the subjectivities that come into being through such processes. It is not surprising that news of America's initial airstrikes in Syria came from the live-tweets of an individual witnessing these strikes in Syria. If the Muslim Arab is the central figure of the mainstream narrative of international conflict, then online firewalls must be kept to a minimum in order to allow these subjects to represent and share their lived experiences to the global community.

Certainly, we should be ambivalent about the Western attacks against ISIS, while also veering away from the rhetoric of Islamophobia. Differentiating between the web propaganda of ISIS—which Western media continuously re-presents—and the shared experiences of Syrian locals is not difficult. It is our responsibility, I believe, to focus our attention on the lives of the Syrian revolutionaries who continue to endure, rather than prove Žižek's claim that Western civilization is “an apathetic creature [Nietzsche's Last Man] with no great passion or commitment” (“ISIS is a Disgrace to True Fundamentalism” 2014). Rather than viewing the re-presentations of ISIS and then uselessly denigrating their fundamentalist claims in the same terms as the “experts” of Islam, we must develop a more rigorous and inclusive methodology to “‘problem-solving’ approaches in the study of ‘terrorism’” by envisioning the subject “at a human level with the purpose of [...] ‘humanizing the other’” (Gunning 363, 378). It is important to remember that the members of ISIS are political subjects and not merely the embodied shades of radicalized Islam. As for the Syrian revolutionaries, they will continue to (com)post their experiences to the world (like any other Westerner on social media), and it is up to the mass audiences to see and listen to what the Syrians have to say about themselves and what they refer to as their home. It is possible that by not releasing images of Osama bin Laden's

body, Obama curtailed the viral “war of images” during the Iraq War (Nicholas Mirzoeff 113). Nevertheless, this does not nullify the need for activity in visualizing the events unfolding in Syria through the Syrians’ revolution of images. What Spivak wanted to see was a “radical anticolonial hybrid space in the metropolis for the public sphere” (81). Today, that space is the cyberscape of social media and it ought to remain that way. For this reason, I agree with Alan Lui’s push for collaboration between the digital humanists and cultural critics—particularly postcolonial scholars—in addressing the concerns of individuals who are in social, economic, and political need (502). This type of “new interpretive and scholarly enterprise” that Said envisioned can work to “reduce the effects of imperialist shackles on thought and human relations” (*Orientalism* 352). Before the data is lost, as we have realized by the history of the Hama Massacre, activists, scholars, writers, and the like must collaborate with the goal of visualizing and sharing these nonsequential experiences of reality.

Works Cited

“About Twitter, Inc. | About.” *About Twitter, Inc. | About*. Twitter, n.d. Web. 08 Dec, 2014.

Ahmed, Nafeez. "Pentagon Preparing for Mass Civil Breakdown." *The Guardian*. The Guardian, 12 June 2014. Web. 10 Dec. 2014.
<http://www.theguardian.com/environment/fearth-insight/2014/jun/12/pentagon-mass-civil-breakdown%3FCMP%3Dshare_btn_fb>.

Baudrillard, Jean. "The Ecstasy of Communication." *The Anti-Aesthetic: Essays on Postmodern Culture*. 126-133. Print.

Chapman, Gary. "Taming the Computer." *Flame Wars: The Discourse of Cyber Culture*. Durham: Duke UP, 1994. 297-319. Print.

Erlich, Reese. *Conversations with Terrorists: Middle East Leaders on Politics, Violence, and Empire*. Sausalito: PoliPointPress, 2010. Print.

Fanon, Frantz, and Richard Philcox. *The Wretched of the Earth*. New York: Grove, 2004. Print.

Ford, Bev, and Corky Siemaszko. "James Foley 'never Cracked' amid ISIS Brutality." *NY Daily News*. NYDailyNew.com, 24 Aug. 2014. Web. 11 Dec. 2014. <<http://www.nydailynews.com/news/world/french-journalist-partly-ids-james-foley-killer-article-1.1912022>>.

Foster, Hal, ed. *The Anti-Aesthetic: Essays on Postmodern Culture*. Townsend: Bay Press, 1983. Print.

Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. New York: Vintage, 1995. Print.

—. *The History of Sexuality: Volume I: An Introduction*. New York: Vintage, 1990. Print.

Gunning, Jeroen. "A Case for Critical Terrorism Studies?" *Government and Opposition* 42.3 (2007): 363-393. Web 5 Sep. 2014.

Hardt, Michael and Antonio Negri. *Empire*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard U P, 2001. Print.

Hayles, N. Katherine. *My Mother Was a Computer: Digital Subjects and Literary Texts*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2005. Print.

"How Schoolboys Began the Syrian Revolution." *CBSNews*. CBS Interactive, 26 Apr. 2011. Web. 10 Dec. 2014. <<http://www.cbsnews.com/news/how-schoolboys-began-the-syrian-revolution/>>.

Janes, Regina. *Losing Our Heads: Beheadings in Literature and Culture*. New York: New York UP, 2005. Print.

Joyce, James. *Ulysses*. South Cresent, London: Wordsworth Classics, 2010. Print.

Karam, Joyce. "Syria's Revolution through the Banners of Kafranbel." *Al Arabiya News*. Al Arabiya Network, 11 Jan. 2014. Web. 10 Dec. 2014. <<http://english.alarabiya.net/en/perspective/analysis/2014/01/11/Syria-s-revolution-through-the-banners-of-Kafranbel-.html>>.

Keats, Jonathan. *Virtual Words: Language on the Edge of Science and Technology*. New York: Oxford U P, 2011.

Liu, Alan. "Where is Cultural Criticism in the Digital Humanities?" *Debates in the Digital Humanities*. Ed. Matthew K. Gold. Minneapolis: U of Minnesota P, 2012. 490-509. Print.

Lyotard, Jean-François. *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*. Trans. Geoff Bennington and Brian Massumi. Minneapolis: U of Minnesota P, 1984. Print.

Massad, Joseph Andoni. "Re-Orienting Desire: The Gay International and the Arab world."

Public Culture 14.2 (2002): 361-385. Web. 20 Nov. 2014.

McAlister, Melanie. *Epic Encounters: Culture, Media, and U.S. Interests in the Middle East,*

1945-2000. Los Angeles: U of California P, 2001. Print.

Mezzadra, Sandro and Brett Neilson. *Border as Method, or, the Multiplication of Labor.*

Durham: Duke U P, 2013. Print.

Mirzoeff, Nicholas. *How to See the World.* Gretna: Pelican, 2015. Print.

Occupied Liberated Kafranbel. Kafranbel Artists, 2014. Web. 10 Dec. 2014.

<<http://www.occupiedkafranbel.com/>>.

Said, Edward W. *Orientalism.* New York: Vintage, 1994. Print.

—. *Culture and Imperialism.* New York: Vintage Books, 1994.

—. *Covering Islam: How the Media and the Experts Determine How We See the Rest of the World.* New York: Vintage Books, 1997. Print.

—. "Opponents, Audiences, Constituencies." *The Anti-Aesthetic: Essays on Postmodern Culture.* 135-159.

Sinclair, Samuel J. and Daniel Antonius. *The Psychology of Terrorism Fears.* New York: Oxford U P, 2012. Print.

Spivak, GayatriChakravorty. "Globalities: Terror and Its Consequences." *CR: The New Centennial Review* 4.1 (2004): 73-94. Web. 12 Nov. 2014.

Thiong'o, Ngũgĩ wa. *Globalectics: Theory and the Politics of Knowing*. New York: Columbia U
P, 2012. Print.

Ulmer, Gregory L. "The Object of Post-Criticism." *The Anti-Aesthetic: Essays on Postmodern
Culture*. 83-107.

Žižek, Slavoj. "ISIS Is a Disgrace to True Fundamentalism." *Opinionator*. The New York Times
Company, 03 Sept. 2014. Web. 11 Dec. 2014.
<[http://opinionator.blogs.nytimes.com/2014/09/03/isis-is-a-disgrace-to-true-
fundamentalism/?_php=true&_type=blogs&_r=0](http://opinionator.blogs.nytimes.com/2014/09/03/isis-is-a-disgrace-to-true-fundamentalism/?_php=true&_type=blogs&_r=0)>.

—. "Syria Is a Pseudo-struggle." *The Guardian*. The Guardian, 6 Sept. 2013. Web. 10 Sept.
2013.
<<http://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2013/sep/06/syria-pseudo-struggle-egypt>>.

—. "Welcome to the Desert of the Real." *The South Atlantic Quarterly* 101.2 (2002): 385-389.
Web. 15 Nov. 2014.